

An Academic Review on the Evaluation of Important Criteria in the Diagnosis and Treatment of Bipolar Disorder

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Abstract

There is not enough research available currently to arrive at any definitive findings on the prevention of functional impairment in people with BP. The symptoms of inter-period residual depression are reported by more than half of the individuals who have been diagnosed with bipolar disorder (BD) (De Dios et al. 2010; Gitlin et al. 1995). Patients suffering from these symptoms are unable to fully live their life that is feasible for them. Subthreshold depressive symptoms, when combined with neurocognitive impairment, may be one of the most accurate predictors of functional outcome in this setting (Bonn et al. 2010, 2012, 2014; Reinares et al., 2013; Martinez-Aran and Vieta 2015; Samalin et al. al.al).2017). This was found in a study done by Bonn et al., Reinares et al. These results were previously published in Bonn et.'s in 2010, 2012, and 2014. On the other hand, it is possible that the relationship between functional result and subthreshold depressive symptoms is not as straightforward and unidirectional as it appears; rather, the two

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appear to impact one another (Gitlin & Miklowitz, 2017; Weinstock & Miller, 2008). The presence of residual depressive symptoms is a significant factor that contributes to relapse (Vieta and Garsia, 2016; Radua et al., 2017). This factor influences psychosocial functioning as well as quality of life (Bonn et al., 2012; Xiang et al., 2017). 2014). In addition to this, the impact of persistent depressive symptoms on functional outcome are also being considered. Thankfully, an unmet need in the treatment of persistent depression symptoms following a stroke is being addressed by clinical studies researching how to treat them. These trials are looking at how to treat them. A recent randomized controlled study (RCT) indicated that the effectiveness of quetiapine with 300 mg daily supplementary extended salami in the treatment of subthreshold depression symptoms was considerably greater than that of placebo (gar Riga et al. 2017). The functional result, on the other hand, did not show any meaningful signs of improvement. There are several different reasons that this may be the case; one of them is that the sample size wasn't large enough to identify any significant differences in the secondary outcome. With relation to an exceedingly small number of psychological therapies, subthreshold symptoms were also addressed in some of them as the primary result.

Keywords: *Bipolar Disorder, BD Diagnosis, BD Treatment, BD Diagnosis and Treatment Criteria*

Introduction

To the best of our knowledge, there has only been one pilot randomized controlled study (RCT) performed to investigate how Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing treatment helps this specific type of symptomatology. At the 12-month follow-up, patients in the treatment group exhibited a statistically significant improvement in depressed and hypomanic symptoms when compared with patients in the control group who received therapy as usual; however, the patients' psychosocial functioning was not evaluated (Novo et al. 2014). According to Moreno-Alcázar et al. (2017), a considerable number of further focused investigations are now being carried out with the goals of reducing symptoms and relapses and enhancing psychosocial functioning. A wider pool of participants will be used for this investigation. In terms of FR, secondary analyses have revealed that persons with subsyndromal symptoms can also improve their psychosocial functioning because of therapy. [Citation needed] (Sanchez-Moreno et al. 2017).

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According to González-Isasi et al. (2014), it has also been demonstrated to be helpful in reducing the severity of symptoms while simultaneously enhancing social and vocational functioning. Additional treatments include a strategy that evaluates the efficacy of an intervention that combines cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and psychoeducation over a longer period. This is one example of a therapy. It has been demonstrated that this therapy is successful. It has also been discovered that cognitive behavioral therapy has positive benefits on a person's social functioning (Lam et al., 2003).

Both Interpersonal and Social Rhythm

After being put through a randomized clinical study that was done by Inder and colleagues (2015), patients showed substantial improvements in both their depressive and manic symptoms, as well as their ability to function socially. It has been demonstrated that individuals with bipolar disorder who are experiencing acute depressive episodes can benefit from intensive psychotherapy (family-focused therapy [FFT], interpersonal and social rhythm therapy, or cognitive behavioral therapy) in terms of their functional outcomes (Miklowitz et al., 2007a).

Finally, it has been demonstrated that the use of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy is highly effective in the treatment of anxious and depressed symptoms (Williams et al., 2008; Ives-Deliperi et al., 2013; Perich et al., 2013). It is feasible to postulate that the treatment of sub-threshold depressive symptoms may be an indirect means of enhancing psychosocial functioning, however further study is required to confirm this hypothesis. Medication is just one part of the overall treatment plan for this condition. Although lithium is the antiepileptic and antipsychotic medication of choice for most patients undergoing pharmacological therapy, additional antiepileptics and antipsychotics such valproate and carbamazepine may also be utilized.

Method

Planning for preventative therapy as part of the treatment of bipolar disorder is done in combination with the treatment of the disease phases at each stage of the condition. This assures that the patient will not become ill in the future because of this treatment.

It is of the utmost importance to identify the early warning signs of the disease to begin treatment at the earliest possible stage. It is possible for the patient's friends and family to become aware of

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these warning indicators by drawing their attention to them and describing their significance to them. It is in everyone's best interest to stay as close to the patient as possible during this time of year, when the weather is transitioning from one season to the next. It is important for the patient to pay attention to any warning symptoms that manifest themselves. During this period, the patient should refrain from ingesting any sort of alcohol or other drugs, including opioids. It is important for him to establish and stick to a consistent sleep schedule and to make certain that he receives adequate rest each night. It is equally as crucial to obtain this quantity of sleep each night as it is to acquire a total of eight hours of sleep each day. If the patient begins to experience severe bleeding, he should get in touch with his family and his physician as quickly as possible. It is an exceedingly difficult method to try to manage the condition after waiting for it to grow more severe before trying to treat it. When treatment is started earlier, patients have a better response to therapy.

In addition, it is essential to safeguard the patient's finances against the chance of suffering a loss by removing credit cards from his possession, handing over the keys to the patient's vehicle in a methodical manner, and conducting follow-up conversations during this time of the year. The following are some of the warning signs that you should keep an eye out for:

- (1) *The desire not to sleep or sleep.*
- (2) *Behaviors that make people's lives unbearable.*
- (3) *Too many ideas running through his head.*
- (4) *excessive talkativeness*
- (5) *Easily aroused or feeling restless*
- (6) *spend money recklessly*
- (7) *Significant changes in both your appetite and weight.*

Bipolar disorder (BD) is a significant and chronic mental health illness that is defined by recurring mood episodes ranging from depression to manic states and variations in energy levels. BD affects around 1% of the general population. Around one percent of the general population is affected with BD.

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Bipolar I illness (BD-I) is one of the most common forms of BP. Bipolar II disease (BD-II), which combines a manic episode with mood abnormalities such as a hypomanic episode or a depressed episode, needs the presence of at least one depressive episode.

A person is said to be in a state of euthymic when they do not suffer from any mood disorders. The onset of BP is often during the early years of adulthood, and it is estimated that the lifetime prevalence of BD-I is 0.6% and that of BD-II is 0.4% across the globe. Individuals who have high blood pressure are at an elevated risk for both mental health disorders and the physical diseases that often accompany them. It is possible that the risks of dying prematurely due to suicide as well as other medical issues such as cardiovascular or respiratory disorders are higher than they are in the general population. Hayes et al. According to the findings of a meta-analysis conducted by the standardized death rate (SMR) for deaths from all causes was determined to be 2.05. It was discovered that the SMRs for suicide and unnatural death were the highest, coming in at 14.44 and 7.42, respectively. Moreover, BD results in enormous expenditures being incurred by society.

The effects of BD can have a significant negative impact on daily activities in many aspects of a person's life, including but not limited to interruptions in basic functionality, work, and social duties. This can have a significant negative impact on a person's ability to function normally in their daily life.

are most impacted, and this includes activities such as personal care, home duties, employment, and leisure. Every fundamental action or combination of routine tasks that are related to autonomous functioning in day-to-day life are included in Oya's by BD. When discussing activities of daily living (ADLs), it is usual practice to differentiate between two distinct categories:

“basic activities of daily living (BADLs) and instrumental activities of daily living (IADLs) or extended activities of daily living (EADLs). The ADLs that make up the 12 BADLs usually include basic self-care actions such as moving, eating, dressing, grooming, and using the bathroom.

Literature Review

Functionality and performance in ADLs are often much lower in individuals diagnosed with BP, as indicated by the outcomes of original research studies studying the association between mental health and functioning. Even after the patient's BP has been successfully treated, research shows

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that their ADL performance and engagement in the BP community remain impaired. In addition, between 30 and 60 percent of those who have suffered with GH never regain their previous level of functioning. Decker et al. The researchers found that the patients' capacity to conduct activities of daily life dramatically declined over the course of their remission in the study that they conducted with 43 individuals. These dysfunctions manifested themselves in the form of increased physical exertion, weariness, or disorganization in anywhere from 20% to 50% of these individuals. Because of this, having high blood pressure has a significant effect on the ability to conduct the activities of everyday life, even when the symptoms are quite minor. In addition, recovery models demonstrate that the absence of symptoms does not result in increased functioning; hence, individuals who are no longer receiving direct treatment for BP are not likely to exhibit improvement in their functioning. It is vital to consider which parts of functioning in everyday activities are most strongly affected in order to further minimize societal expenses, which frequently continue to contribute considerably to those costs. In the most recent studies, BP is investigated in terms of social ties and work environments most of the time. According to the findings of several studies, social functioning can be negatively impacted in a variety of ways, including a reduction in the frequency of social interactions and feelings of discomfort in social settings. It is also possible that this has influenced interactions with spouses, extended family members, and close relatives. Similarly, it appears that bipolar illness has an effect on employment, where the employment rate varies from 40% to 60%, and if they are working, they may be more prone to take days off from work and underperform at their job. In addition, the employment rate ranges from 40% to 60%.

need to be involved frequently in their daily activities, including the management of their household responsibilities, finances, and personal hygiene. If a person's ability to manage their daily routine is impaired, it is likely that they will have difficulty maintaining their relationships and/or their position at work. It is not known whether ADLs are directly engaged in BP or if there is any pattern in the functioning of ADLs, even though there is broad interest in the functioning of ADL in all BP diagnosis.

According to recent research, patients with BP have difficulty doing an increasing number of the many ADLs that are being investigated. 26 In addition, there are primary studies that have been

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conducted to investigate how performance is related to functioning in the workplace and social settings in a variety of ADL areas. The findings of these studies have been summarized in terms of the degree of ADL functioning in subsets of ADLs such as personal care, domestic activities, and fiscal management. There is not yet a systematic review available currently. This systematic review will be conducted with the intention of assisting medical professionals in gaining a better understanding of the types and subgroups of ADLs that patients with BP typically struggle with, as well as the level of ADL independence or performance that patients with BP typically have. When people's degrees of independence in executing various ADLs are investigated, it can serve to affect both the practical and therapeutic modalities that are used in therapeutic settings. This can be achieved by giving therapists with certain locations where they should think about intervening in the patient's treatment.

In most cases, we will do our research searches with the following search terms and their many derivatives:

"activities of daily living", "functional independence" and "bipolar disorder"

It is probable that some studies were ignored; thus, checking the reference lists of other included research is an excellent approach to locate relevant published publications that cannot be identified using the search strategy. This is because there is a possibility that some studies were overlooked. The program for managing reviews is called Covidence, and it will be used to compile all the studies that make it through the first and second levels of the scan.

Instrumental activities that include carrying oneself, managing one's finances, shopping, cooking meals, managing domestic duties, or managing medications are examples of ADLs that might be classified as instrumental. This assessment could contain several different indicators for assessing the operational performance of AIs. The UCSD Performance-Based Skills Assessment, the Lawton IADL scale, the Katz Index of Independence in Activities of Daily Living, the Performance Assessment of Self-Care Skills, the Functional Assessment Quiz, and other related performances are some examples of the types of assessments that fall under this category. Metrics that are based on data that have been previously verified in adult or older adult populations should also be considered essential.

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The use of self-reported measurements, such as the Activities of Daily Life Questionnaire, is another option that might be considered. There will be a differentiation established between data that is based on performance and data that is self-declared.

Exclusion Conditions

Studies that do not assess functional performance in terms of ADL will be excluded from consideration for inclusion in the review. Also, if ADL performance or independence is measured across multiple ADLs, this indicates that the participant did not describe functioning in specific ADLs, such as grooming or administering medications. This is because measuring ADL performance or independence across multiple ADLs is more comprehensive. This is since such a measurement does not offer a meaningful representation of the participant's functioning as a whole. Even if there is currently study on social functioning, work, and BP, such research will similarly be overlooked if it focuses exclusively on work or employment or social functioning without paying attention to BADLs or IADLs. Although there is already research on social functioning, work, and BP. Studies that describe ADL performance or functioning in various mental health problems worldwide, such as reporting ADL performance with schizophrenia or major depressive disorder, will not be considered for inclusion in this review because those studies do not describe ADL performance or functioning. The research that looked at persons who have comorbidities in addition to high blood pressure will not be counted toward the total. Co-morbidities can manifest themselves in a wide variety of ways, including but not limited to diseases, diagnoses of cancer, issues related to substance addiction, developmental delays, or other mental health conditions. This evaluation does not consider any publications that investigate comorbidities and BP without making a distinction between the illnesses on their own. This is since research looking into comorbidities can also have an effect on a person's capacity to do an ADL.

While determining whether the articles satisfy the inclusion requirements, there will be a screening process comprised of two stages. The examination will begin with this initial stage now. When it is time for the second screening round, the two reviewers will evaluate whether all of the articles that made it through the first screening round fit the inclusion standards. This evaluation will take place after the time for the second screening round has passed. The scanning process is going to be conducted twice, once for each level. Any disagreements on articles that fulfill the prerequisites

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for inclusion will be settled either by collective consensus or, if that fails, through discussion with a third impartial arbitrator.

Data Collection

After the initial round of screening, the researchers will manually collect all the pertinent data from the publications that made it through, and then they will save it in a piece of review management software called Covidence. A data extraction form will be utilized to collect information for the necessary objectives.

Critical Evaluation

These definitions pertain to the same kind of agitation that may be seen in a person's mental state and are commonly used interchangeably to refer to the same condition: manic-depressive illness, often known as bipolar disorder. Although the first signs of bipolar illness often manifest themselves between the ages of 15 and 25, a person might develop the condition at any time in their life. The years between the ages of 15 and 24 have the highest incidence rate when compared to other time periods. It presents itself in the form of manic, hypomanic, and depressive episodes in that order. It causes difficulties for the individual in a variety of spheres, beginning with their educational life and going beyond. The individual's environment may be aware of the symptoms, but the individual normally does not have any consciousness of himself or himself at all.

During an assault, the target has the potential to hurt themselves or their surroundings. On the other side, the individual has a propensity to direct most of his hostility and damaging behavior onto himself. If a person with bipolar disease is not properly recognized or treated, they run the risk of committing suicide or engaging in other risky behaviors, either of which might result in their death. While treating the disease, it is optimal to employ a combination of medicine and psychotherapy for the best results. The method of therapy will benefit enormously from this change. Although 15% of patients make a full recovery from the disease, 45% of patients are likely to experience a recurrence at some point in their lifetime. In the next section of this article, we will discuss in greater depth the factors that lead to the condition, the symptoms that accompany it, and the approach that is used to treat it.

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It will have a detrimental impact on the individuals' educational, professional, and social life if they do not receive treatment for their bipolar condition, or if they begin therapy but do not see it through to its conclusion. The onset of symptoms between the ages of 15 and 24 corresponds with a particularly pivotal time in the formation of a person's professional life, which highlights the significance of this age range. Between the ages of 15 and 18, people frequently make decisions that will have a significant impact on their lives in the years to come.

“such as the subject of education, choosing a university and choosing a job”

Those who are in their 20s are frequently in the midst of their college education, first career experiences, internships, and opportunity to network. The challenges that an individual must overcome throughout this time, when focusing on one's own personal, professional, and social growth ought to be the individual's top priority, are not interchangeable with one another. Because of this, academic endeavors or professional occupations are often consigned to the background for those who show indications of bipolar disease. The difficulties in a person's conduct, in addition to that person's lack of consistency, can cause damage to the connections that person has with their family and the surroundings.

People frequently get borderline personality disorder and bipolar disorder mixed up with one another since their symptoms are so similar.

What is Borderline Personality Disorder?

It is a state of mind that last for a considerable amount of time, and different persons may be susceptible to attacks at various periods. It can occur as manic episodes, hypomanic episodes, or depressed episodes. In certain quarters, it is also referred to as manic-depressive disorder or bipolar mood disorder. Furthermore, the term "bipolar" may also be used. Because this is a mental condition, the typical course of treatment involves the use of medicines. It is extremely advised that the treatment procedure include psychotherapy as one of its components. People can display signs of manic or hypomanic mania, significant depression, or both at the same time. Whenever a person with bipolar illness goes through an episode, they will exhibit odd conduct, which will draw the notice of those who are observing them from the outside. There is an about 2% prevalence rate of bipolar disorder in the general population, and the risk of acquiring this condition is essentially

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the same for both men and women. In addition to a person's overall quality of life, it is thought that certain life experiences might bring on a manic-depressive condition, which is thought to be caused by a genetic component. During a manic episode, the individual suffering from the condition is extremely upbeat, energetic, and active. The person's upbeat and cheerful outlook might come off as unsettling to other people. It is not difficult to experience happiness as well as rage. His response is sometimes overly aggressive, particularly when he is placed in circumstances that involve displeasure, pressure, or criticism. Mania is characterized by a decline in a person's capacity to operate regularly and preserve harmony. This is one of the defining characteristics of the manic state. There is evidence of overly dramatic conduct, participation in activities that might put the individual in harm's way, and uncontrolled expenditure of money. This disorder is characterized by the occurrence of hypomanic episodes occasionally.

Findings

Hypomania is a kind of manic illness that is significantly less severe. Although the symptoms are comparable, the person's usual functioning performance and level of productivity are far less severely disrupted in hypomania as compared to mania. As a direct consequence of this, members of the social circle have a more tough time identifying episodes of hypomania. An episode of manic-depressive disease is referred to as "hypomania" when the signs of mania are present, although they are present at a substantially lower intensity than usual. A manic episode is characterized by an extremely euphoric feeling, which is the exact opposite of a depressed mood. At this period, it is possible for depressive symptoms to present themselves. These symptoms may include, but are not limited to, thoughts of worthlessness or guilt, emotions of melancholy, weeping, lack of energy, loss of enjoyment, and problems sleeping. What are the indications and manifestations that point to a diagnosis of bipolar disorder? When a person with bipolar illness is experiencing a manic episode, they will feel an extreme amount of energy, happiness, and hyperactivity. On the other hand, when a person is going through a depressive episode, they could feel hopeless, like they are locked in a routine, sad, or even like taking their own life. At this time, the individual may choose to cut links with his family, friends, and any obligations that have been placed on him. Both the ability to care for oneself and to function normally will decrease. The following is a list of symptoms that can be observed in patients suffering from both manic and

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depressive periods. At least three of the symptoms of manic depression need to be present each day for at least a week before a diagnosis of manic depression may be established.

It is usual to have at least five symptoms for a period of at least two weeks while a person is in the depressed phase of the illness.

Manic Episode Symptoms

- (1) *Sleep-related disorders (decreased need for sleep, difficulty falling or staying asleep, or frequent waking)*
- (2) *Very high and happy mood (euphoria)*
- (3) *High levels of energy, restlessness, hyperactivity, and increased activity*
- (4) *Difficulty keeping one's self in focus of attention and concentration .*
- (5) *Increased urge for sexual activity*
- (6) *Overspending, gambling, and shopping that are both uncontrollable and unnecessary*
- (7) *Lack of reasonable expectations about one's own abilities*
- (8) *increase in the substance of thinking and speech increase in the content of provocative action and inappropriate*
- (9) *During the manic phase of the illness, a person with bipolar disorder may also use more alcohol and other substances.*
- (10) *Increased dangerous behavior with high adrenaline levels*
- (11) *Signs and symptoms of mood disorder are hopelessness,*
- (12) *pessimism feeling gloomy and unhappy*
- (13) *Frustrated, unable to enjoy life that is too tense*
- (14) *Decreased desire to engage in sexual activity*
- (15) *energy consumption carelessness*
- (16) *Forgetfulness and difficulty remembering things*
- (17) *concentrating on things, a sense of lack of self-worth*
- (18) *Changes in eating patterns; loss of appetite or overeating may also be present.*
- (19) *Waking up several times during the night*
- (20) *Sleeping a lot, having trouble falling asleep or staying asleep during the day,*
- (21) *Negative feelings such as powerlessness and worthlessness*

(22) *Having suicidal or suicidal thoughts*

The diagnosis method for manic-depressive disease must always begin with observation and assessment in a clinical environment. These steps are absolutely necessary. However, in order to arrive at a clear diagnosis, a psychiatric evaluation is necessary, and several tests, scales, and inventories may be utilized in the course of this assessment.

There are two stages involved in the treatment of bipolar disorder:

“Treatment of acute exacerbations and preventive therapy”

Each stages are essential in their own right. The medication plays a significant part in the overall course of the condition's recovery from being treated. Therefore, taking medicine on its own is not adequate as a kind of treatment. It is advised that patients seek assistance through psychotherapy in addition to medical treatment for their condition. Patients who are being treated by psychologists and psychiatrists who are qualified to provide therapy might benefit from this type of assistance. During psychotherapy, the goal is to establish skills for coping with stress in addition to reducing the impact of stress factors that may trigger manic or depressive episodes. These things have the potential to be triggers. In addition to the hereditary predisposition that is already there, it is theorized that neurotransmitters have a role in the development of the mental disease known as bipolar disorder. These neurotransmitters are in charge of ensuring proper growth of the brain as well as communication between different brain cells. There is a possibility that, in addition to the signs of bipolar illness, there will also be symptoms of other conditions. These conditions include, but are not limited to, issues related to food, anxiety, substance addiction, obesity, migraine headaches, thyroid illness, and heart disease. It is necessary to diagnose and treat any secondary illnesses that may be present in addition to the underlying ailment that is being treated.

stop the growth of the disease and lessen the intensity of the symptoms. Individuals should, in addition to taking medicine and participating in psychotherapy, adapt to the environments in which they find themselves and obtain psychological assistance.

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How Can Bipolar Disorder Symptoms Be Managed and What Can Be Done?

It is advised that individuals participate in activities that improve the quality of life in order to either forestall the progression of the disease or lessen the intensity of its symptoms. It is extremely necessary to get a sufficient amount of sleep on a regular basis, and it is also very important to schedule the final activity of the day before going to bed, as well as the first activity of the day after waking up.

Do something soothing like reading a book, listening to music, or meditating before going to bed instead of spending time on the phone. This will help you wind down and get ready for sleep. One of the things that can be done to make it easier to manage the symptoms of a bipolar disorder is to learn how to breathe correctly and do exercises that focus on breathing.

Before getting out of bed in the morning and again before going to sleep at night, a specific amount of time should be set aside to perform exercises that focus on deep breathing. It is essential to set dietary patterns that are not only healthy but also balanced, and that are appropriate for one's age as well as one's body type. Use of caffeine should be avoided, as should diets that are heavy in carbs. The individual should seek the advice of an appropriately trained medical practitioner in order to devise an acceptable diet plan, and then they should make every attempt to adhere to the plan in as rigorous of a manner as is humanly feasible. It is not urged that you embrace the diet in order to reduce weight or avoid disease; rather, it is recommended that you adopt the diet as a lifestyle.

It is strongly advised that the amount of physical activity guidelines be raised. Even devoting as little as ten to fifteen minutes to a variety of different types of physical activity on a daily basis will have a beneficial influence on the way the illness develops. One of the most important things that might play a part in the onset of symptoms that are connected with bipolar disease is stress. The disorder can be triggered and symptoms might become more severe when a person is under stress in their personal, professional, social, or educational lives.

As a consequence of this, it's in your best interest to steer clear of the more stressful areas of life whenever it's feasible to do so. The use of alcohol and other substances, if any, should be limited, and if at all feasible, their use should be avoided completely. It is necessary to learn how to deal

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with stressful circumstances. It is vital to learn how to cope with stressful situations. It is essential not to lose sight of the fact that consuming alcohol and engaging in the use of other substances are fantastic methods to bring on the disease and exacerbate the symptoms of it.

Anger is a common emotion experienced by people who are experiencing manic episodes. Nonetheless, despite the fact that the person's primary target is themselves, their fury is quite intense. Also, there are times when a hostile and angry attitude toward the surrounding environment might be detected.

The patient should make an effort to enhance their capacity to control their anger, and others with whom the patient speaks regularly should, if at all feasible, make an effort to develop their own abilities in controlling their anger as well.

When Someone with Bipolar Disorder Goes Untreated, How Does It Affect Their Lives?

It is possible for people who are afflicted with manic-depressive disease to either be unable to identify their symptoms or to choose to ignore them. Particularly the symptoms that start in adolescence may be evaluated as a puberty effect by the family and the surroundings. Especially the symptoms that start in adolescence can be evaluated as a puberty effect. Because of these characteristics, people who attend a college that is located a significant distance from their home, live by themselves, have few social contacts, and work irregular hours may have a more difficult time detecting the indicators of their disease.

Those who struggle with bipolar illness frequently aren't aware that they have the condition's symptoms. Because of this, the beginning of the therapy is held off. The direction and support of the family or community may be quite helpful in the first phases of the therapeutic process. Failure in school is always a risk for children and teenagers whose illnesses go undetected and untreated. A poor academic performance may be brought on by a number of circumstances, including distraction, difficulties concentrating, absenteeism, and behavior that violates the norms. Several individuals struggle to get themselves ready for college, to prepare well for tests, or to do well in academic disciplines.

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How Can a Person's Personality Best Develop in the Context of the Ideal Family Environment?

Reading our articles might also provide you with something that is valuable to you. Individuals who have been diagnosed with bipolar illness are more likely to suffer from adverse academic outcomes, such as dropping out of school or being expelled from their current educational setting. Things that can be noted in university education include absenteeism, difficulties in social communication, and behavior that goes against the regulations. They could have difficulty communicating with others who are in positions of authority. Those who are socially isolated and do not have a support system are at a much increased risk of attempting suicide.

It is not unusual for candidates seeking positions in the business sector to be unsuccessful in job interviews, to fall short of the performance standards required in the business world, and to often move employers. When there are two parties involved in an interaction, there is always the potential for a disagreement between the two parties. It's possible that keeping the social peace and sustaining friendships will be challenging at times. These individuals have a higher risk of being divorced and switching love partners on a regular basis. There is also the potential of demonstrating a parenting attitude that is inconsistent while carrying out one's responsibilities as a parent. It is feasible to make the move from working in a field that demands one to be exceedingly loving, caring, hopeful, and helpful to working in a field that requires one to be furious, contentious, and aggressive. When one considers all of this material, it becomes abundantly evident that the treatment of bipolar disorder, which is both a psychological and a psychiatric condition, is something that simply cannot be disregarded. It is feasible, while receiving treatment for this condition, to remove the potentially detrimental effects that are linked with it.

both while receiving treatment and afterwards. With time, an individual will develop abilities that pertain to social cohesiveness, increased self-awareness, increased productivity, and increased sustainability.

The mental disease known as bipolar disorder, or BPD for short, is characterized by periods of both elevated and sad moods alternating in a person's lifetime. The person who has bipolar disorder goes through significant changes, some of which include intense feelings of unhappiness, bursts of energy, and a variety of different emotional states such as helplessness, hopelessness, suicidal

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ideation, worthlessness, and pessimism. In addition, the individual with bipolar disorder may experience significant changes in their physical appearance. Bipolar disorder can potentially induce suicide.

The mental condition known as bipolar disorder, which is more often known as manic depression, is marked by excessive high and low emotions, as well as changes in sleep, activity, thinking, and behavior. Manic depression is another name for bipolar disorder. Those who suffer from bipolar illness may go through phases in which they are incredibly upbeat and full of energy, and they may also go through periods in which they are terribly down, hopeless, and sluggish. People usually remark that they are feeling fully normal during this interim period. The fluctuations in one's mood, which may be thought of as two separate "poles" of mood, are the reason for the disease being referred to as "bipolar disorder." The condition of feeling excessively exuberant and confident is referred to as "manic," and it is used to describe how a person who suffers from bipolar disease may feel at times. These emotions can also result in impatience, impulsive behavior, or the irresponsible abandoning of a situation. Hallucinations are when a person sees or hears things that are not there, but delusions are when a person believes something that is not true and cannot be deduced from it. Around half of the persons who have mania also have hallucinations and delusions at the same time. The word "hypomania" refers to the less severe symptoms of mania, in which a person does not suffer delusions or hallucinations and their manic symptoms do not interfere with their day-to-day living in any significant way. A person is considered to be "depressed" if they have strong feelings of sadness or depression and the term "depression" describes them. These symptoms are identical to those that are outlined in major depressive disorder, which is more often referred to as "clinical depression." The absence of hypomanic or manic episodes in a patient with clinical depression distinguishes this form of depression from other types of depression. The majority of persons who suffer from bipolar disorder are more likely to experience depressed symptoms than manic or hypomanic ones.

Do You Have Multiple Bipolar Disorders?

There are several different types of bipolar disorder, including:

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Bipolar I disorder: In this type, behavior is extremely erratic and there are periods of at least one week of or severe manic "elevation", requiring medical treatment. There are also typically prolonged intense "down" seizures that can last for at least two weeks.

Bipolar type II disorder: If this type of illness is present, there will still be irregular ups and downs, but they will not be as severe as those associated with bipolar type I disorder. Cyclothymic disorder is a type of bipolar disorder characterized by alternating phases. Manic and depressive behaviors are observed for at least two years in adults and at least one year in adolescents and teenagers. Symptoms are not as severe as those associated with bipolar disorder type I or type II.

used to describe situations in which a person shows only a few of the mood and energy signs that define an episode of manic or hypomanic behavior in another individual. It's possible that the symptoms won't stick around for long enough to be classified as "episodes." It is essential to keep in mind that fast cycling is not a subtype of bipolar disease; rather, it is a phrase that is used to define the course of the illness in individuals who have bipolar I or II disorder. Applicable if a person experiences at least four episodes of depression over the course of a single year. This particular symptom of the illness is more common in females than it is in males, and it might make an appearance at any time in the course of bipolar disorder or vanish completely without warning. Depression is the key factor that drives the fast cycle, which is linked to an increased chance of having suicide thoughts or actually following through on those ideas.

In all of its manifestations, bipolar disorder can be made worse by the use of drugs and excessive amounts of alcohol. A person who is suffering from a "dual diagnosis," often known as bipolar illness and alcohol use disorder, should seek medical assistance from a physician who is capable of treating both diseases.

What Signs and Symptoms Are Associated with Bipolar Disorder?

Bipolar disorder is characterized by dramatic bursts of high and low moods, yet these episodes do not follow a pattern that makes them predictable. It is conceivable for a person to experience the same mood over and over again, such as despair or mania, before flipping to the feeling that is the complete opposite of the previous one. In other situations, these episodes might stretch out over the course of several weeks, months, or even years. The severity to which it is manifested varies

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from one individual to the next, and it also has the capacity to alter over time, becoming either more severe or less severe. There is a possibility that you might experience symptoms known as "highs."

Conclusion

It's probable that the manner in which your brain develops also plays a part in this phenomenon, even if experts aren't totally certain on how or why it occurs. When a person is in their late teens or early 20s is a regular time for them to experience their first symptoms of bipolar disease. Very seldom, it can also manifest itself in younger children. It's possible that someone in your family has bipolar disorder. The bad luck befalls both men and women in equal measure. A "quick cycle" is characterized as four or more different mood episodes occurring within a single calendar year. As compared to males, women have a slightly higher probability of suffering a rapid cycle than men do. Women who suffer from bipolar disorder are more likely to undergo spells of depression than males who have the condition. Women typically do not exhibit symptoms of bipolar disease until considerably later in life, and those who do are more likely to have bipolar disorder II and be impacted by seasonal mood swings. In general, women do not show indicators of bipolar illness until much later in life. Women also have a higher propensity to experience mental and physical health disorders at the same time, which is a trend that tends to be more prevalent in women. Some examples of such medical disorders include thyroid illness, migraine headaches, and difficulties related to anxiety. People who suffer from bipolar disorder have an increased risk of developing other mental health conditions, such as seasonal depression, co-occurring anxiety disorders, post-traumatic stress disorder, and obsessive-compulsive disorder. This risk is increased because people with bipolar disorder already have a higher risk of developing bipolar disorder.

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